

ISic0874

I.Sicily inscription 0874

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) Κ(αταχθονίοις)
2. [Μην]ώφιλε ΚΕΙΣΑΙ
3. τελευτᾶν φατο μόρσιμον

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492502

EDCS 39102029

PHI 140353

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

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Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5419

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